

PSSOH post-conference

“Linux installation workshop” organized by PSSOH

At this workshop, we will help participants to install linux on their old devices (with emphasis on tablets, especially with old 32-bit BIOS). A special flavor of Ubuntu Linux called Xubuntu will be installed, which is extremely lightweight and therefore suitable for old hardware. We can also install linux on regular laptops, or bring someone’s old laptop back to life. Participants should bring their own tablets or laptops, but it is open to everyone who is interested in just watching and asking questions. Please, note that the number of participants will be limited in accordance with the local COVID-19 pandemic recommendations.

11:00 – 11:20 Introduction

Nikola Todorović, Nebojša Jovanović

11:20 – 12:20 Installation of Linux

Nikola Todorović, Nebojša Jovanović, Sara Živković, Danilo Đokić

Language: Serbian

Date & time: October 16 , 2021 (PSSOH post-conference day) at 11 am, CET

Place: laboratory 69 and Zoom, University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering, Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

URL: <http://pssoh.etf.bg.ac.rs/>, contact: pssoh@etf.bg.ac.rs

PSSOH post-konferencijska

“Radionica instaliranja linuksa” u organizaciji PSSOH

Na ovoj radionici ćemo pomoći učesnicima da instaliraju linuks na svoje stare uređaje (sa naglaskom na tablete, posebno sa starim 32-bitnim BIOS-om). Pokazaćemo kako instalirati derivativ Ubuntu Linuksa pod nazivom Xubuntu, koji je izuzetno lagan i samim tim pogodan za stari hardver. Takođe, pomoći ćemo učesnicima da instaliraju linuks na svojim laptopovima ili oživeti nečiji stari laptop. Učesnici treba da ponesu svoje tablete ili laptopove, a radionica je otvorena i za sve ostale koji su zainteresovani samo da gledaju i postavljaju pitanja. Broj učesnika će biti ograničen u skladu sa trenutnim lokalnim preporukama u vezi sa COVID-19 pandemijom.

11:00 – 11:20 Uvodna prezentacija

Nikola Todorović, Nebojša Jovanović

11:20 – 12:20 Instalacija linuksa

Nikola Todorović, Nebojša Jovanović, Sara Živković, Danilo Đokić

Jezik radionice: srpski

Datum i vreme: 16. oktobar 2021 (post-konferencijski dan) sa početkom u 11 časova

mesto: laboratorija 69 i Zoom, Univerzitet u Beogradu – Elektrotehnički fakultet, Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Beograd, Srbija

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